

The Future and Journey of Social Media Towards Virtual World

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Abstract:- Social media has covered and permeated the entire human life and also existence of human beings. Sociability is a basic human characteristic and gossiping is an integral part of social dialogue. Social Media is a highly developed form of social gossiping. In one click we can interact with any person from any country in the world through social media. Friendship and interaction with many people at a time is an important feature of social media. Social media allows sharing of feelings. Ideas and information is exchanged through social media. Social contact continues to grow day by day. There are lots of examples people help each other through social contact. Despite these many benefits, social media cannot demonstrate spatial presence. Although social media enhances interaction, it represents a virtual existence. Obviously, virtual world issues also come into focus on social media. Hence, an anonymous fear seems to be forming that social media is not moving towards the virtual world. Many problems arise in the virtual world, whether it is family or social, its consequences can be felt by the entire human race. The virtual world will remain a superficial and imperfect world. The virtual world is not perfect and how to deal with it is a huge challenge. Good and bad effects of social media also affect your emotions. Social media creates problems with properly controlling and channeling emotions because it creates emotional hanging. Mental pressure builds up as emotions go up and down. Mentally, the person also becomes depressed. The use of social media reduces efficiency. As the time that should be spent on productive work is not available, it has a far-reaching impact on overall growth. Due to social media there is a huge increase in cyber crime. Overall, people are still experimenting in the virtual world of social media and facing lot of issues in adjustment. In this article we try to find out in which direction this journey of the virtual world is going? What are its possible side effects? And information about how all mankind will find a way out of it has been made available.

Keywords:- Social, Virtual, Media, Communication, Interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Food, clothing, and shelter are the basic human needs. Now, social media has become the fourth basic need. Some day before, some important applications in social media were shut down and life seemed to come to a standstill. Communication has been a natural gift from immemorial times. The discovery of scripts and languages has

revolutionized human communication. Script is a distinctive writing system, based on a repertoire of specific elements or symbols, or that repertoire. Language is the system of communication in speech and writing that is used by people of a particular country. There are two types of communication one is verbal and another is non verbal. In ancient period we can find some of the oldest forms of human communication include making sounds, drawing or painting, dancing, acting, and using symbols. The journey of communication includes Cave Paintings, Smoke Signals, Carrier Pigeons, Postal System, Newspapers, Radios, Telegraph, Telephone, Television, Internet, Email, Text Message and Social media. The Internet has made evolution of communication more effective. We can send messages with just one click. Computers, mobile phones, laptops, radios, etc, all help us to communicate. The latest mode of communication in the digital world is the social media. People share their entire life events on social media. Social media platforms help people share pictures, videos, and almost everything on the internet. Social media has reduced the geographical boundaries and distances between two people and the time gap has been reduced to a fraction of a second. All in all, social media has captured the entire human life. Just as the force of gravity works, the social media works to connect the bonds of contact and communication between two or more people. Social media is emerging as a new innovation in human communication. However question marks have been always raised about this. Fake accounts, cyber crime, cheating, pornography, blackmailing, defamation etc. now became common type fraud on social media. Therefore all users are in pressure however they are not able to keep away from social media because there are lot of benefits they are enjoying from social media platform. However there is urgent need to balance the use of social media in our daily life and need to avoid virtual world in life. In this article, we will try to explain the future of social media and the journey towards the virtual world. We also try to shed light on the emergence of the social media and its use and its future.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social media is now spread everywhere in the world. One who said 'no one can survive without social media. It is the fastest medium of communication. Social media encompasses every sphere and corner of mankind. The first recognizable social media site Six Degrees was created in 1997. It helps users to upload a profile and make friends with other users. The first blogging sites became popular in 1999, creating a social media sensation. After the invention of blogging, social media began in popularity. Sites like

MySpace and LinkedIn gained prominence in the early 2000s, and sites like Photobucket and Flickr facilitated online photo sharing. YouTube came out in 2005, creating an entirely new way for people to communicate and share with each other across great distances. In 2006, Facebook and Twitter both became available to users throughout the world. These sites remain some of the most popular social networks on the Internet. Other sites like Tumblr, Spotify, Foursquare and Pinterest began popping up to fill specific social networking niches. Today, there is a tremendous variety of social networking sites, and many of them can be linked to allow cross-posting. This creates an environment where users can reach the maximum number of people without sacrificing the intimacy of person-to-person communication.

Mohammed et al., 2021; observed in research that the social media is becoming a critical part of everyone's life. Social media has numerous platforms including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn. Impersonation is a common phenomenon found nearly on all social media platforms; it is the act of attempting to deceive someone by pretending that he is another person. Impersonators always try to hide a real account by making another similar profile to spread the fake contents on social media platforms making it very difficult to know the real accounts from the fake ones. The article explains on the social media impersonation, impersonation types, how to identify the social media impersonation, cases of social media impersonation, how to prevent impersonation, and how to protect the security of a social media user. Social media impersonation is the act of pretending that a person is another person which usually occurs on all social media platforms.

Messinger, et al., (2009), discussed about the virtual worlds, where thousands of people can interact simultaneously within the same environment, represent a frontier in social computing with critical implications for business, education, social sciences, and our society at large. In this paper, they first trace the history of virtual worlds back to its antecedents in electronic gaming and on-line social networking. They provide an overview of extant virtual worlds, including education-focused, theme-based, community-specific, children-focused, and self-determined worlds and they analyze the relationship among these worlds according to an initial taxonomy for the area.

Madouni, et al., (2020) elaborated about the virtual media emerged and disseminated immensely ; specifically in the last ten years of the twenty first Century, through innumerable channels and virtually broadcasting pages, as strong equivalently as the traditional mass media in almost life critical domains and areas ; as a result and feature of the technological progress. The technology of the twenty-first Century gave to hands a wide reach and availability of information, it allows people and communities to participate even in producing and making influential public opinions towards local and international issues and topical; as ways of social interaction behind devices screens. Technology and changes create a sort of circumstantial adaptation which did not exist before. Furthermore and notably, the traditional mass media amid this advance; they signify regular corners

and a considerable space for the virtual interactions of intellectual and popular society categories; through the worldwide known media and interactive gates.

Gogolin, et al. (2014) critically discussed about the use of virtual worlds and social media has grown to the point that more than one-quarter of the world's population utilize it in some manner. Security and privacy concerns regarding the use and capabilities of current and emerging technologies such as gaming, blogging, podcasting, virtual meetings, virtual worlds and Web 3.0 is examined. Security and privacy concerns are investigated in the context of exploits, vulnerabilities, and related security risks; confidential access control; communication trends and patterns in the use of massive communication strategies; intellectual property and product risk management; resource management; financial considerations and accountability; and safety. Several technologies and personal practices are reviewed, as well as ways to mitigate or eliminate their associated risks. The core principles of information security-confidentiality, integrity, and availability-provide an overall framework.

Eraslan, et al., (2019), illustrated about the living in the age of constant technology developments shifted social communication patterns and shifted social relations to virtual environments. The socialization process that takes place in digital platforms also transferred many negative elements experienced in social life to the virtual environment. That is, the aggression behaviours concerning these negative processes have also been transferred to the virtual communication. The current study examines the effects of social media aggression (SMA) regarding digital platforms on the social relations in human life in the context of various variables. Results of the study revealed that the counter-comments towards participants' values have a significant effect on participants' demonstration of aggressive tendencies.

Papp, Raymond; (2010), discussed thoroughly about virtual worlds and social networking. As online communication and collaboration becomes more commonplace, universities are exploring the educational possibilities of online virtual environments for reaching the Millennial. Both virtual worlds and social networking constitute a large part of the Millennial' time and incorporating these technologies into the classroom can foster a more collaborative and diverse learning atmosphere. Virtual campus tours, recruiting, advising, simulations and classes are all part of the growing virtual environment. Corporate and educational institutions are exploring their use in cutting costs, delivering higher customer satisfaction and catering to a more tech-savvy clientele.

Pradeep, et al., (2016), shade light on the Social Networking Sites (SNSs) such as Facebook have made inroads in the life of users. The current study used a quantitative approach to explore adolescents usage of SNS in Mumbai and their perceptions and experiences of the same. Easily accessible Internet and availability of devices such as smart phones influenced access to SNS. Computer-mediated-communication was the preferred means of communication.

Selective self-representation and online social comparison were pertinent themes seen through the study. Gender and age differences were found in the overall usage and experiences of SNS.

III. DISCUSSION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Three million years ago, a truly wise man started roaming the earth. For many years, everything went smoothly, such as living in the same territory, roaming for food, and reproducing. Gradually, as man began to comprehend, analyze, and reflect on the information he received, he became involved in the process of evolution. Such an evolution had begun not only on a physical but also on a mental level. As a result, he had to adapt to the environment in which he lived, as his body adapted. However, these changes were taking place at a very subtle and very slow pace. On the other hand, mental changes were advancing at a slower pace, and so human evolution was advancing faster than other animals.

This pace of evolution began with the discovery of fire, increased with the discovery of the wheel, speeded up due with discovery of agriculture, and the discovery of script and language gained real momentum for human evolution and development. Printing, Radio, Internet, and Mobile Phones have brought the world closer together. Social media brought man closer and the geographical distance of man-to-man became zero.

Evolutionary changes are very slow, while revolutions happen in a few years and suddenly. In simple terms, evolution means change and getting used to that change, while revolution is sudden change. Whether social media is evolution or revolution? When changes happen and those changes are not accustomed, it has physical and mental trauma. As the man sat up and started working, he started getting back and neck ailments. As the man gained weight, he began to develop diabetes and high blood pressure. Of course, social media is a part of human evolution or revolution is a subject of research, but the radical changes brought about by social media did not take many years to get used to physically and mentally, and suddenly we started riding on social media. Eventually, many of its good and bad consequences are beginning to emerge. The above mentioned changes, which do not get used to the physical and mental, certainly cause physical and mental disorders. No one should be upset that social media has increased the physical complaints of man. Eye strain, strain on the cervical spine, the effect of mobile light on the skin of the face is some of the complaints that need to be mentioned deliberately. No one should be offended by the fact that mental problems are exacerbated by the slowness of thought processes, constant distractions due to incoming messages, persistence of thought processes, grief and frustration, fear and irritability by mobile and social media as a whole. Everyone has a situation where they understand but do not turn around.

Although social media is not as physically and mentally accustomed as it is, the attraction of the information available and the interaction and communication that takes place is so great that man is drawn to it like a force of gravity. This power does not allow him to sit still and think. As a result, information, data, language, scripts, videos, audio and pictures are simply exploding. How to store so much information is a challenge in front of the brain, so it immediately began to put the information in the dustbin. There is so much information that it takes a lot of time and energy for the brain to grasp and analyze it, so the brain may be stopped grasping and analyzing. It is certainly not desirable for a wise person to accept that the brain is moving in the right direction. Naturally, social media will have far-reaching effects on human comprehension and analysis. Naturally, the connection between the brain and the mind is disrupted. The confusion between what the mind tells the brain and what the brain tells the mind has created confusion and roughness in the emotions that arise from the mind. Therefore, there is an upheaval in happiness, sorrow, anger, fear, hatred, surprise, love.

In the past, we used to express these feelings on occasion, but now they are completely broken. Therefore, emotions and thoughts are harmonized. Everyone is dependent on this social media. The world is constantly changing and science and technology are accelerating this change. As the changes took place, we became more and more aware of that change. But the big question for researchers is whether the current change has brought about mental and physical harmony. Among them, it will be necessary to see whether the massive use of social media and the mental and physical changes it requires are taking place. Mobile and its electromagnetic waves cover the whole world. The mobile revolution happened, but with it came the social media revolution. Social media has shocked many superpowers globally and social media has done a disservice to the family.

We are all connected to the virtual relationship and the virtual world, rather than personal and interpersonal relationships. In a virtual relationship, even though the connection of contacts and communication is fast, they cannot create intimacy. As we aware eyes contact and touches and actual emotional and mental support play an important role in creating intimacy. Virtual relationships seem to lack this. Although social media has accelerated communication and interaction, the disadvantages outweigh the benefits. The benefits of social media are obvious at the business level and at the administrative level; however social media has not been able to work beyond virtual communication at the individual level.

Social media has also contributed to the decline in human efficiency and effectiveness. There is a fear that we will lose creativity and innovation. Although social media is attractive, it is not conducive to long-term human development. The time that you have is so precious that it is spent in the virtual world and just listening to, viewing and reading information so no one else has time left to be for constructive work. There are also some gentlemen who are

spending more than ten hours out of twenty four hours on mobile and social media. The power of human capital as a whole is weakening and diminishing. As a result, its problems are becoming more prevalent in the business, social spheres and at the family level. Going even further, some organized cybercriminals are on the rise, increasing the number of people being deceived in various ways. Fake accounts, cyber crime, cheating, pornography, blackmailing, defamation etc. now became common type fraud on social media. Instead of that the Fake friends, Free app downloads, Quizzes ,Hidden URLs, Lottery and Free Gift Card Scam, Gossip Scam, Healthcare Scam, Cat fishing, Photo of You Scam, Account Cancelled Scam, Nigerian Scam, Stuck Abroad Scam, IQ Scam, See Who Viewed Your Profile Scam etc type of frauds now became very common on social media.

Man is such an intelligent creature on earth that he is always looking for reuse from waste. Naturally, even though the world is occupied by social media, a lot of changes are expected in the future. Also, the use of social media needs to be as efficient and effective as it needs to be. Otherwise the possibility of human beings running away from this social media cannot be ruled out. There is nothing that can defeat a human being, deprive him, because at the same time the human race has many options in front of it and it is capable of choosing the right option at the right time. Although it is not possible to say how long social media will control and cover to human being, many more good and bad effects of social media are yet to come. Naturally, the four generations that exist on the surface of the earth need to use social media in a timely, limitedly, efficiently, effectively and to make human life simpler, easier, straightforward, convenient and enjoyable.

IV. CONCLUSION

The changes are inevitable we can't deny it. The social media is one of the major changes in our daily life. It is now became a part and parcel of our routine life. No one can avoid it and no one can deny it. Social media has touched every aspect of human life and made it easy and comfortable. Smart phones and social media are the inventions of science and technology. Social media has definitely revolutionized for human life. Social media works on the three goals that are communication, relationship and interaction. Social media brings two or more people together so the exchange of feelings and thoughts takes place at a faster pace. Useful information is also available quickly through social media.

Social media has permeated and covered the entire life of human being although it has also been created some serious problems for mankind. This will include unnecessary information bombardment, spreading false and misleading information, inflammatory emotions, wastage of time, and absenteeism from work and cyber crime, family conflict. These all problems are the due to virtual feature of social media. The entry and spread of this virtual world is a challenge created by social media for the entire world. Since the virtual world is mostly superficial, nothing substantial happens in it. The virtual world is shallow in nature. Relationships in this virtual world are not that much

permanent. Emotions cannot be controlled and flowed properly in virtual world because the reality is different. Taking all these factors and things for granted, there is a global need for a comprehensive effort to stop the society polarization towards a virtual world. We need to realize that social media is a necessity not a must. Anything in this world is difficult but not impossible.

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